

GLH. Longevity of adult GLH on the seedlings also was evaluated. Plants were scored 3 wk after inoculation for symptoms and assayed by latex test for the presence of the rice tungro bacilliform (RTBV) and spherical (RSTV) viruses.

ARCI 1554, Gam Pai 30-12-15, Kataribhog, and Utri Rajapan showed low level of apparent RTV infection but were mostly infected with RTBV alone, regardless of the number of insects used for inoculation (see table). Average vector longevity was shorter on ARCI 1554 and Gam Pai 30-12-15, indicating resistance to GLH, and longer on Kataribhog and Utri Rajapan, indicating low resistance. TKM6 and ASD7 showed apparent RTV symptoms even when infected with RTBV.

Longevity of adult GLH, percentage of seedlings with apparent symptoms, and infection by RTBV and RTSV of rice varieties exposed to 1 or 5 RTV-viruliferous GLH. IRRI, 1987.

Variety	GLH longevity (d)	Seedlings infected ^a (%)							
		1 insect/seedling			5 insects/seedling				
		With apparent symptoms	By latex test			With apparent symptoms	By latex test		
RTBV+ RTSV	RTBV		RTSV	RTBV+ RTSV	RTBV		RTSV		
TN1	9.4	13	43	33	4	74	61	32	2
TKM6	1.3	47	0	48	0	39	3	46	0
Gam Pai 30-12-15	4.9	13	0	19	0	13	0	49	0
ASD7	3.8	33	7	38	4	46	25	47	2
Utri Rajapan	8.4	4	2	7	0	7	3	22	0
ARCI1554	4.1	0	0	11	0	11	0	22	0
Kataribhog	9.4	28	5	73	2	25	14	60	0

^aAv of 2 trials. Plants scored and assayed by latex test 3 wk after inoculation.

Kataribhog had low infection on the basis of symptoms but had high RTBV

infection, indicating symptomatic resistance (tolerance) to RTV. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

INSECT RESISTANCE

Tolerance of some rice varieties for gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason

P.S. P. Rao, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack 753006, Orissa, India

Thirty-day-old seedlings of 15 varieties were transplanted singly at 15- × 15-cm spacing in two 18- × 3-m plots per entry

on 29 Jul 1982 to synchronize the vulnerable tillering stage with high GM infestation. The varieties were grown with 80 + 20 kg N, 18 kg P, and 33 kg K/ ha.

One plot of each variety was protected with granular diazinon applied to soil water at 1.50 kg ai/ha on 10, 25, and 40 d after transplanting (DT).

Because the experimental field tended to

be invaded by other insects (leaf folder, yellow borer, etc) from 40 DT, all plots were sprayed with 0.4 kg ai phosphamidon/ha at 40, 50, 60, and 70 DT.

Twelve 9-plant samples were marked at random in each plot. Percent silvershoots (SS) was estimated at 50 d after treatment and grain yields were recorded at harvest.

Vikram, PTB10, and CR94-MR1550

GM incidence and yield losses in some rice varieties. CRRI, Cuttack, 1982 wet season.

Variety	Seed to 50% flowering (d)	GM incidence (%)			Regression equation for expected yield (kg/ha)	Regression (r) value	% yield loss/unit % incidence	Reaction ^a to pest based on	
		Lowest	Highest	Mean (24 samples)				Incidence	Yield loss
GEB24	116	0	95	50	3161 - 19.6 ×	-0.747**	0.62	S	LT
Pankaj	113	10	91	46	1301 - 59.1 ×	-0.900**	0.81	S	LT
CR94R-MR1559	104	14	94	59	3119 - 34.1 ×	-0.699**	0.93	S	LT
Vijaya	96	17	93	54	4099 - 21.8 ×	-0.777**	0.68	S	LT
Sona	96	11	88	56	3321 - 11.3 ×	-0.802**	0.52	S	MT
Jaya	90	11	90	60	5913 - 55.2 ×	-0.887**	0.93	S	LT
CR58-MR1538	85	10	62	29	5658 - 62.6 ×	-0.747**	1.11	S	LT
Padma	82	18	91	49	2194 - 14.2 ×	-0.625**	0.51	S	MT
Bala	65	10	40	25	2405 - 23.5 ×	-0.450*	0.98	S	LT
Leuang 152	138	0	0	0	-	-	-	HR	-
Vikram	96	0	39	13	6072 - 32.2 ×	-0.282	0.53	R	-
CR94-MR1550	95	0	46	8	5588 - 28.0 ×	-0.215	0.50	R	-
PTB10	70	3	24	9	2112 - 1.6 ×	-0.151	0.35	R	-
CR1014	121	0	78	34	2569 + 1.3 ×	+0.342	-0.06	S	HT
Jagannath	113	0	80	35	4798 - 12.8 ×	-0.457*	0.27	S	HT

^aPercent silvershoots. S = susceptible, R = resistant, HR = highly resistant, LT = least tolerant, MT = moderately tolerant, HT = highly tolerant.

rated resistant, with means of 8-13% SS; Leuang 152 was highly resistant (no SS).

The correlation of incidence with yield was negatively linear except for CR1014. In 10 varieties, the regression coefficient was significant or highly significant (see table).

Yield loss ranged from -0.06% in

CR1014 to 1.1% in CR58-MRI538. Based on yield losses, susceptible entries could be tentatively classified for tolerance as follows:

Highly tolerant : CR1014,
(0-0.30%) Jagannath
Moderately tolerant : Sona, Padma
(0.31-0.60%)

Least tolerant : GEB24, Pankaj,
(0.61%–higher) CR94-MRI559,
Vijaya, Jaya,
CR58-MR1538,
Bala

As yield loss varied widely among varieties, economic injury and threshold levels also varied. □

Stem borers (SB) in dryland and wetland rice

A. T. Barrion and J.A. Litsinger,
Entomology Department; E. Sison and
M. Arrauadeau, Plant Breeding Department,
IRRI

We compared SB infestation in an

irrigated wetland field planted to *indica* varieties and in a dryland field planted to *japonica* varieties. The experimental fields were planted the same day.

At 2 wk before harvest, 150 tillers/variety were dissected. SB infestation was higher in the japonica varieties (see figure). SB species found in

wetland indicas and dryland japonicas also differed.

Five SB sp. were collected in both rice environments: *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker), *C. auricilius* Dudgeon, *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker), *Maliarpha* sp., and *Sesamia inferens* (Walker). Species abundance in the indicas was *S. incertulas* > *C. auricilius* > *C. suppressalis* > *S. inferens* > *Maliarpha* sp. In the japonicas, it was *C. suppressalis* > *C. auricilius* > *S. inferens* > *Maliarpha* sp. > *S. incertulas*.

The indicas had fewer whiteheads (1-4%) and SB (4-12 larvae) than the japonicas (1-12% whiteheads and 0-130 SB larvae). Four Brazilian japonica varieties — Japones, Maranhao Vermelho, Manteiga, and Poupa Preguica — had the highest infestation. □

Species composition (%)

Stem borer larvae (no./150 tillers)

Whiteheads (%)

Relative abundance of rice SB in *japonica* varieties planted in dryland fields and *indica* varieties planted in wetland fields. IRRI farm, 1985 wet season.

Screening of rice accessions against leaf folder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*

R. Rajendran and R. Velusamy, Centre for Plant Protection Studies, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore 641003, India

We screened 32 rice accessions from the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project for resistance to LF during 1986 wet season, using a seedling screening technique.

Pregerminated seeds of accessions were sown 6 cm apart in 6 rows in 50- × 40- × 10-cm wooden seedboxes. Each accession was planted across the width of the seedbox to maintain at least 5 hills (3 plants/hill)/row. One row of susceptible check TN1 and one row of resistant check Ptb 33 were sown at